

EXPLORING LANGUAGE-AGNOSTIC SPEECH REPRESENTATIONS USING DOMAIN KNOWLEDGE FOR DETECTING ALZHEIMER’S DEMENTIA

Zehra Shah, Shi-ang Qi, Fei Wang, Mahtab Farrokh,
Mashrura Tasnim, Eleni Stroulia, Russell Greiner*

Manos Plitsis, Athanasios Katsamanis

Department of Computing Science
University of Alberta, Edmonton, Canada

Institute for Language and Speech Processing,
Athena Research Center, Greece

ABSTRACT

We explore ways to use speech data to screen for indications of Alzheimer’s dementia (AD). In particular, we describe our approach to the ICASSP 2023 Signal Processing Grand Challenge, which involves extrapolating from models learned from English speech samples, to Greek speech samples, to determine which subjects have AD. By using acoustic and linguistic features, inspired by clinical research on AD, our top-performing classification model achieves 69% accuracy in distinguishing AD patients from healthy controls, and our regression model attains an RMSE of 4.8 for inferring cognitive testing scores. These outcomes underscore the potential of our explainable model for detecting cognitive decline in AD patients via speech, and its applicability in clinical settings.

Index Terms— Alzheimer’s dementia; Speech; Machine Learning; Signal Processing

1. INTRODUCTION

With global population aging at an accelerated pace, worldwide prevalence of Alzheimer’s dementia (AD) is also on the rise. This motivates today’s significant interest in developing automatic, inexpensive, and scalable methods to support early diagnosis of AD. Since AD is characterized by a progressive decline in cognitive abilities, potentially leading to speech and language impairment, the analysis of speech signals for AD detection holds great potential.

In this paper, we present our methods for tackling the ICASSP 2023 Signal Processing Grand Challenge: “ADReSS-M: Multilingual Alzheimer’s Dementia Recognition through Spontaneous Speech” [1], which sought methods for detecting dementia from speech signals whose predictive performance is preserved across two different languages. Given a set of *English* speech samples of subjects describing a specific picture, Challenge participants submitted models that were then tested on *Greek* speech samples of different subjects, describing a different picture. Our submission explored

various acoustic and language feature representations, based on pre-trained speech and language embeddings as well as conventional acoustic and linguistic feature extraction methods. Our best-performing classification model used a feature set based on language features derived from word-level attention maps, a representation of the distribution of pauses, and participant’s meta-features (age, gender, and education), with PCA for dimension reduction followed by a logistic regression model, to obtain a test set accuracy of 69.57%. Our best regression model applied support vector regression to a representation of the distribution of pauses (silent segments) in the audio files and meta-features as the input features, to obtain a test set root mean squared error (RMSE) of 4.77 – leading to an overall fourth ranking.

2. DATA SET AND EVALUATION

The training data set contained 237 age- and gender-balanced audio files of English speech samples as well as associated meta-data (age, gender, education) and labels (Control vs ProbableAD for classification, and MMSE scores for regression). We were also given a small set of 8 Greek audio samples, with metadata and labels. To evaluate our models and to set the hyperparameters, we used stratified 5-fold cross-validation (5SCV) on a fixed set of age-, gender-, and label-balanced folds over the English data. We used the set of 8 Greek samples as a separate hold-out test set.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Feature extraction

Automatic Speech Recognition: `Whisper` [2] is a state-of-art Transformer-based multilingual speech-recognition model that is capable of both transcribing given audio and also translating audio context to another language – *eg.* Greek audio to English text. Here, we used the `Whisper-Large` multilingual model to transcribe all audios and created translations for each Greek speech audio using the same model. In our work, we did not directly utilize transcripts or translations. However, we found that the word-level features extracted from the model were highly beneficial.

*The authors would like to acknowledge Bahareh Behroozi Asl, Weijie Sun, and Amir Salimi for their support in developing our submission.

Fluency and intelligibility: Many studies suggest that fluency and intelligibility may be important indicators of cognitive decline and AD – eg, AD patients (1) speak at a slower rate than healthy older adults [3]; (2) often exhibit increased levels of disfluency (pauses, hesitations, or disruptions) in their speech, increasing as the disease progresses [3]; and (3) often exhibit reduced speech intelligibility, which can make it more difficult for them to communicate effectively with others [4].

Therefore, we compute the following three sets of features:

(1) *Word-level durations feature set* describes whether the speakers are mostly using short or long words, and how quickly they are uttering them. We obtained the duration of each word in an audio recording using a modified version of Whisper model¹, which uses attention weights from cross-attention mechanisms and dynamic time-warping methods to determine start and end timestamp of each word. Note this method does not account for gaps between words. For each audio sample, we compute the total number of words in the speech, as well as the mean, maximum, minimum, and standard deviation of the word durations.

(2) *Pause rate feature set* describes the distributions of detected pause segments in spontaneous speech. We identified the voiced and unvoiced segments of the audio using the openSMILE toolkit [5], which also provided the timestamps of the onset of voiced segments, along with their duration. We used this to compute 11 features related to silence and length of audio segments. Besides some basic features like pause length means and variances, we also derived features by fitting different probability density functions (PDFs) to the histograms of total silence durations for cases versus controls over the complete audio sample, and the histograms of lengths of unvoiced audio segments for cases versus controls. We then used the means and variances of these fitted PDFs as input features for our models.

(3) *Speech intelligibility feature set* describes the ease and accuracy with which a listener can comprehend the speech, which here is represented by the word-level confidence score assigned to each recognized word by a speech-recognition model. The confidence score for each word is expressed as the predicted probability of each word from the Whisper model. As with the word-level duration feature set, we compute the mean, maximum, minimum, and standard deviation of the confidence scores for every word in the speech. Additionally, we include a log-sum score of all confidence scores to represent the model’s confidence in the entire transcript.

3.2. Modelling

To identify the optimal pipeline, we considered several dimension reduction techniques – including Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Latent Semantic Analysis – and

many base learning algorithms – Logistic regression, random forest, support vector machine (SVM), extreme gradient boosting, and neural networks – using different combinations of the extracted features mentioned above. We employed internal 5SCV to fine-tune the hyperparameters of each model based on accuracy and RMSE.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our internal cross-validation identified the classification model with the best performance: Apply logistic regression with L2-regularizer, to the features corresponding to the top 10 PCA components of the union of meta-features, word-level duration, pause rate, and speech intelligibility; this yielded mean accuracies of $74.70 \pm 4.90\%$ (resp., 75%) on the 5SCV English dataset (resp., 8 Greek samples). On the competition’s Greek test set, the accuracy dropped to 69.57%.

For the regression task, we trained an SVM (with a radial basis function kernel and regularization parameter set to 1) on a combination of the meta-features with the pause features, of the English dataset. This produced a 5SCV RMSEs of 6.487 ± 0.696 (resp., 3.13) on the 5SCV English dataset (resp., 8 Greek samples). On the test set, the RMSE was 4.7693.

Note that many previous models used thousands of text embedding features and acoustic features, which makes them difficult to explain and, by implication, to trust. In contrast, both of our models focus on features thought to be relevant to diagnosing AD – here, utilizing only 24 features: 3 meta features, 5 for speech rate, 11 for pause rate, and 5 for speech intelligibility. Collectively, our outcomes show that machine-learned models can detect cognitive decline from speech, even when trained on different languages (learned from English, then used in Greek), and slightly different tasks (different pictures).

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Luz et al., “Multilingual alzheimer’s dementia recognition through spontaneous speech: a signal processing grand challenge,” *arXiv:2301.05562*, 2023.
- [2] Radford et al., “Robust speech recognition via large-scale weak supervision,” *arXiv:2212.04356*, 2022.
- [3] Roark et al., “Spoken language derived measures for detecting mild cognitive impairment,” *IEEE – Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 2011.
- [4] Kempler et al., “Language and dementia: Neuropsychological aspects,” *Annual review of applied linguistics*, 2008.
- [5] Eyben et al., “Opensmile: the munich versatile and fast open-source audio feature extractor,” in *ACM Int’l Conf on Multimedia*, 2010.

¹<https://github.com/openai/whisper/tree/word-level-timestamps>